

Digitalization of the intangible cultural heritage of the Pomaks of Xanthi

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Abstract

In this paper the language and the oral tradition of the Pomaks of Western Thrace is studied as a part of their intangible cultural heritage. Digital technologies can play an important role in the preservation and transmission of intangible cultural heritage. In Greece, audiovisual material from the Rhodope region dates back to the 1960s. In 1995 the "Thrace" project was launched, focusing on the collection of folk songs and extracts of speech from various villages of Thrace. The "CT-Audio Link" web project (2015-2016) included digitized recordings of Pomak songs, fairy tales, proverbs, wishes, curses and excerpts of spoken word. We present "Philotis", a research project implemented at the Athena-Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies / Xanthi's Branch (2020-2023). "Philotis" focuses on the creation of the infrastructure, the methodology and the tools for the recording, analysis and documentation of living spoken languages, with emphasis on idiomatic language. The infrastructure is characterized by state-of-the-art multimodal technologies (text, image, audio), while the tools integrate into an advanced digital platform for language analysis and documentation using machine learning techniques. The development support framework utilizes modern technology and adapts to the specific needs and characteristics of the individual languages, offering methodology, good practices and digital services. Among the project outputs are a morphosyntactically annotated Pomak corpus that is openly available, a gold annotated corpus on the UD treebank repository, an Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) and Text-to-Speech (TTS) model, and multiword expressions (MWE) documentation. Innovative research projects make available cultural resources that could not be easily developed otherwise. Therefore, the use of new technologies for the preservation and dissemination of the intangible cultural heritage of the Pomaks offers fertile grounds for significant applications in the fields of sociological and linguistic research, folklore studies and education.

1. The significance of intangible cultural heritage

The promotion of intangible cultural heritage is considered to be a priority for many countries all over the world. Intangible cultural heritage (ICH), encompasses folklore, traditions, language, knowledge, customs, beliefs, rites, rituals, ceremonies, indigenous knowledge, social customs, arts, crafts, music, oral traditions, performing arts, social practices, rituals, festive events, cybercultures in the digital world, and emerging new cultures which will become the heritage of the future.

In contrast to cultural homogeneity, cultural diversity is significant at the local, national, and worldwide levels, as it reflects the need to preserve fragile aspects of human civilization which are worth preserving (Zaffwan Idris 2016: 1-11). ICH, "transmitted from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their

history, and provides them with a sense of identity and continuity, thus promoting respect for cultural diversity and human creativity”¹.

Digital technologies may assist the analysis of cultural heritage in many ways. In order to promote various digital applications have been recently used such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), geographical information systems (GIS), 3D modelling, gaming and social media, crowd sourcing, facial expression analysis and modelling, vocal tract sensing, body motion and gesture recognition, encephalography analysis, semantic multimedia analysis, visualization, text-to-song synthesis (Economou 2015: 217-223, Alivizatou-Barakou et al. 2017: 7-22) etc.

According to the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage², the term ‘intangible cultural heritage’ means the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artifacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. This intangible cultural heritage, transmitted from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their history, and provides them with a sense of identity and continuity, thus promoting respect for cultural diversity and human creativity. For the purposes of this Convention, consideration will be given solely to such intangible cultural heritage as is compatible with existing international human rights instruments, as well as with the requirements of mutual respect among communities, groups and individuals, and of sustainable development.

Intangible Cultural Heritage, as defined above, is manifested inter alia in the following domains: (a) oral traditions and expressions, including language as a vehicle of the intangible cultural heritage; (b) performing arts; (c) social practices, rituals and festive events; (d) knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe; (e) traditional craftsmanship.

ICH is, by its own nature, of a markedly dynamic nature. On the one hand, Intangible Cultural Heritage recreates itself in order constantly to reflect the cultural identity of its creators. In fact, such a heritage has the intrinsic capacity to modify and shape its own characteristics in parallel to the cultural evolution of the communities concerned, and is therefore capable of representing their living heritage at any moment. On the other hand, the ‘ephemeral’ character of Intangible Cultural Heritage – makes it particularly vulnerable to being absorbed by the stereotyped cultural models prevailing at any given time (Lenzerini 2011: 118).

Digital efforts have been increasingly employed in recent years to preserve and disseminate ICH assets.

Nowadays it is important to re-examine the rationales behind the whole lifecycle of ICH digitization, which encompass what to document, how to archive, the schema of encoding and modeling, and lastly, the forms of presenting and interpreting knowledge proper for active transmission. (Hou, Kenderdine, Picca, Egloff, Adamou 2022: 12).

As new tools are constantly developed all over the world in order to ensure the widespread adoption of digital surrogates, a discussion of the principles that should be followed is under way (Idris et al. 2016. Giglito et al 2019. Skublewska-Paszkowska et al. 2022). Among these principles are tolerance of diversity, democratization of technology, authenticity, reliability, simplicity, ease of use and

¹ UNESCO (2003). Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage. 1,2, <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0013/001325/132540e.pdf> Accessed on 5/5/2023· also see Silberman 2007· Kearney 2008· Styliaras et al. 2010.

² UNESCO (2003). Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage. <https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/01852-EN.pdf> Accessed on 8/6/2023. Definition of Intangible Cultural Heritage see Cadavez 2022: 45.

improved compatibility with existing working cultures (Mudge, Ashley, Schroer 2007).

It is estimated that in Western Thrace there are more than 35,000 Pomaks (Adamou & Fanciullo 2018) who live in the southern foothills of the Rhodope Mountains as well as in the Thracian plain. They speak Southern Rodhopean dialects, which have remained unwritten until recently. These dialects are used exclusively for oral communication in the family and village micro-society (Klimova, Uzeneva 2022: 150).

The use of modern technologies for the preservation and distribution of the ICH of the Pomaks has major applications in the domains of sociology, linguistics, folklore studies and education. In this paper we will present the attempts that have been made in Greece to record the ICH of the Pomaks. We will also present the “Philotis” project, a project that aims to facilitate the development of linguistic written and narrated resources, especially targeting living languages and dialects at the limits of survival. “Philotis” is a research and infrastructure action, implemented at the ATHENA Research Centre, under the “Action for the Support of Regional Excellence”, funded by the Operational Project “Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation” (NSRF 2014-2020) and co-financed by Greece and the European Union (European Regional Development Fund).

In the last decades a lot of research has been done on the language spoken by the Pomaks of Western Thrace. The vocabulary of the language was thoroughly investigated in various dictionaries (Theocharidis 1996b, Theocharidis 1996c, Karahóĝa 1996, Karahóĝa, Delivasilis, Papathomas 1998, Karahóĝa 1998, Karahóĝa 2017, Karahóĝa 2021). Papadimitriou (2013) described the local dialects of the following Pomak villages: Eranos, Sminthi, Glafki, Kotyli, Kentavros, Ehinós, Satres, Pachni, Oreon, Dimarion, Thermes. Moreover, Pomak Grammar and Syntax were presented and analysed by various authors (Dimopoulos, Doulopoulos, Karahóĝa, Moumin, Papademetriou 1996, Theocharidis 1996a, Katsavelis, Papademetriou, Dimopoulos, Karahóĝa, Mumin 1997, Papademetriou 2008). Linguistic research carried out in the Pomak villages of Xanthi includes significant theses and articles by Pomak linguists (Aziz 2010, Kehaya 2015) as well as other researchers (Kyranoudis 1997, Kyranoudis 1996-98, Constantinides 2008, Adamou 2010, Adamou 2011, Sandry 2013, Constantinides 2020, Krimpas 2020). There are also short presentations of Pomak (Karahóĝa 2006) as well as language course books (Kokkas, 2004).

Various scripts and orthographies have been used in Pomak textual legacy, ranging from Bulgarian-based Cyrillic to Modern Greek to an English-based Latin alphabet. Homogenisation of these texts in order to form a processable corpus required the adoption of a common script and a common orthography. To this end, the Latin-based alphabet proposed by Ritvan Karahóĝa and P. Krimpas was adopted by the “Philotis” project.

K&K alphabet, RODOPSKY-2021	International Phonetic Alphabet (I.P.A.)	Cyrillic alphabet	Examples
æ, æ̂	/æ/	Я, Ъ	<i>snæk</i> (snow), <i>nevæsta</i> (bride)
y, ý	/i/, /u/	Ъ	<i>kysmét</i> (fate), <i>pýtom</i> (ask)
ø, ø̂	/œ/, /ø/	ЬО	<i>spöm</i> (sleep), <i>móso</i> (meat)
ü, ü̂	/y/	Ю	<i>chüvál</i> (sack), <i>lülka</i> (swing)
č	/tʃ/	Ч	<i>čôran</i> (black)
š	/ʃ/	Ш	<i>šápka</i> (bonnet)
c	/ts/	Ц	<i>cístem</i> (clean)
ž	/ʒ/	Ж	<i>žolt</i> (yellow)

ǵ	/dz/	тз	<i>tzvâzda</i> (star)
ǧ	/dʒ/	дж	<i>ǧümayá</i> (mosque)
j	/j/	й	<i>játse</i> (very), <i>jam</i> (eat)
ŋ	/ɲ/	ñй	<i>kócaŋe</i> (cutting)
!	/ʎ/	лй	<i>vasiláz</i> (king)

Table 1. Some letters of the K&K alphabet.

The K&K alphabet was developed to satisfy the following requirements: portability of the alphabet (use of UNICODE), phonetic transparency, easily learned representations of sounds due to the use of similar diacritics for same articulation sounds and the absence of digraphs and consistent spelling not affected by predictable allophony. It should be noted that the K&K alphabet is based on the dialect of Myki but it can also partially serve as a hyperdialectal script by allowing various predictable pronunciations of the same graph according to dialect.

2. Recording and digitization of the language and culture of the Pomaks of Xanthi

Comparative studies in the field of Balkan folklore have identified many common elements in the folk poetry of the Balkan peoples. Musical and folklore recordings in the villages of Western Thrace began late, after the 1960s. The reasons for the delay are related to historical and political causes (domestic and foreign policy issues, the isolation of the mountain communities, the Cold War climate, the different orientation of folklore studies in Greece, the fluidity of the identity of the Pomaks, etc.) (Kokkas 2022: 30-38). As a result of this delay, the Greek literature concerning the oral tradition of the Pomaks of the Greek part of Rhodope is relatively limited.

The first musical productions of traditional songs of the Pomaks were made with three cassettes published in Komotini by the "Thracian Society". The first cassette, entitled "Pomácki Pésne" (1996), contained 14 songs from Glafki, Pachni, Sminthi, Gorgona and Thermes. The second cassette, entitled "Jótfare Kúrse péngüret" (1997) contained eleven songs from Glafki, Pahní and Gorgona.

As regards the oral tradition of the Pomaks of Western Thrace, few texts have been published to date. Among the collections of folklore material are those of the Folklore Laboratory of C. A. Megas (1964), the Folklore Department of the Faculty of Philosophy of the University of Ioannina (1983), the Folklore Department of the Faculty of Philosophy of the University of Thessaloniki (1986), the Centre for the Study of Greek Folklore of the Academy of Athens (1961-1962). The research carried out by Petros Theocharidis during the years 1964-1970 was most significant.

The first music cds were released after the year 2000. Particularly important were Ali Rongo's recordings from Glafki, which were recorded in three books (Rongo 2002, Rongo 2004, Kokkas & Rongo 2005), two of which include inserts. This was followed by two important albums of songs by Mustafá Ahmečík, published in 2002 in Xanthi. In 2003 Vangelis Doropoulos edited the publication of an important album with songs from Oraion, Thermes, Sminthis and Glafki. In 2005, a collective album with songs from the villages of the Kimmeria and Askyra region was published by the P.A.KE.THRA. The cd, published in 2008 by the Foundation of Thracian Art and Tradition, also edited by us, contains 18 songs from Echinós, Dimario, Myki, Glafki, Oreon, Satres, Revma, Temenos and Sminthi. Another notable recording effort is that of Ali Rongo, who has collected songs, tales and proverbs from the Glafki area. The musical interpretations of Eminé Bourouǵí have been published in three albums (2006, 2008, 2011).

The audio archive of Petros Theocharidis is one of the most important steps taken for the digitization of the folk music of the Pomaks. Petros Theocharidis (born in 1934) taught at the Islamic School of Echinus from 1964 to 1971. During those years he recorded the customs and the oral tradition of the Pomaks of Xanthi. He typed on a typewriter a multi-page (457 pages) work entitled "Pomaks, the Muslims of Rhodope. History, origin, language, religion, folklore"³, which contains, among other things, traditional tales, folk songs, riddles and proverbs of the Pomaks, and provides a wealth of information on their history, language, education, material life, family and social life. This work was published in book form in 1995 by the Cultural Development Centre of Thrace (P.A.KE.THRA.). The songs of the Theocharidis collection were republished in 2018 by the Cultural Association of Pomaks of Xanthi.

P. Theocharidis is the author of the following books: *Πομάκοι. Οι Μουσουλμάνοι της Ροδόπης* (Pomaks. The Muslims of Rhodope 1995), *Πομακο-Ελληνικό Λεξικό* (Pomak – Greek Dictionary -1996), *Ελληνο-Πομακικό λεξικό* (Greek – Pomak Dictionary - 1996), *Γραμματική της Πομακικής Γλώσσας* (Grammar of the Pomak Language - 1996). His audio archive consists of recordings which were made in the villages of Xanthi in 1968. The recordings were saved in four analog audio tapes, which were digitized in 2016 (Theocharidis 2018: 16-18). Most of P. Theocharidis' recordings in the villages of Xanthi were made in 1968 and were included in four tapes. In 2013 the 4 tapes were soon digitized. Each tape had two recording sides. The audio tracks had to be segmented and audio edited, which was done in 2016. This was followed by the juxtaposition of the songs with those included in P. Theocharidis' book.

For the classification of the songs, P. Theocharidis had created a table giving each song a serial number, together with an additional number referring to the typed collection that had preceded it. In the manuscript table he indicated the name of the song, the number in the collection, the number on the cassette, the instrument, the singer and the content of each song. The last column of this table is titled "Contents". Here the songs are classified thematically according to their content (historical, dance, parody, mocking, etc.).

The technical problems of the archive's tapes (low volume in some songs, noise, cutting of songs before the end, etc.) do not deprive the collection of its enormous importance, as the material recorded by P. Theocharidis is amenable to further linguistic, folkloric and ethnomusicological analysis.

The image shows a handwritten table with several columns. The columns are labeled at the top: 'Αριθμ. τραγουδιού' (Song Number), 'Αριθμ. συλλογής' (Collection Number), 'Αριθμ. κασέτας' (Cassette Number), 'Όργανο' (Instrument), 'Αρτιστής' (Singer), and 'Περιεχόμενα' (Contents). The table contains numerous rows of handwritten entries, each representing a song with its corresponding details. The handwriting is in Greek and is somewhat dense, filling most of the page.

³ Greek Folklore Research Centre of the Academy of Athens, No. 3249. Petros Theocharidis was awarded in 1970 for his work by the Academy of Athens, while D. Mantzouranis, General Inspector of Foreign and Minority Schools, had also congratulated him in a letter on 27/2/1968.

Figure 1. Classification of Pomak songs in the audio archive of P. Theocharidis. (Theocharidis 2018: 16).

The dvd included in Theocharidis 2018 book (divided into folders corresponding to six cds) that accompanies the book includes 117 traditional Pomak songs and 10 Muslim hymns recorded in 1968. The Pomak songs come from 10 different Pomak villages in the mountainous region of Xanthi and were performed by 14 singers. The total time of the Pomak songs is 5 hours and 26 minutes. The 10 religious hymns have been recorded by students and teachers of the Muslim School of Echinós. The total time of the Muslim hymns is 61'53". The total time of the 6 discs is 6 hours, 14 minutes and 39 seconds.

CD	POMAK VILLAGES	NUMBER OF SONGS
1	OREON (Jasí Erén)	8
	REVMA (Kurú Čái)	7
2	MANTENA (BasáJkovo)	19
3	MANTENA (BasáJkovo)	7
	GORGONA (Bratánkovo)	17
4	AKREOS (Dóljovo)	9
	TEMENOS (Ĝamí maalé)	2
	THERMES (Lýĝa)	14
5	ECHINOS (Šahín)	8
	GLAFKI (Salishtá / Gökčé Bunár)	20
	PACHNI (Pašavík)	6
6	RELIGIOUS HYMNS	10

Table 2. Contents of the 6 disks contained in the audio archive of P. Theocharidis

Most of the recordings were made in Echinós by his students, in the house where Theocharidis lived at the time. However, the collection also includes performers who were not his students, such as Hussein Mehmetali, who was then a shepherd in Mantaina, and Raif Moula Hasan from the village of Oreon. At the time of recording the songs, Raif was about 50 years old. Raif (who passed away in 2006) played bouzouki and accordion.

The recordings of Pomak folk songs made in Greece after the 1960s only marginally managed to rescue a primary material, which was in the process of disappearing. The importance of these recordings for today's researchers is immense, as they constitute a basis for the evolution of the language and music of the Pomaks of Thrace.

Apart from the Theocharidis archive, the existing audiovisual material from the Rhodope Mountains is scarce. After the monumental recordings of Peter Theocharidis in 1968, it took three decades to make new recordings with digital sound and visual recording machines. Important recordings of Pomak songs were made after the 1970s.

However, apart from the song recordings, the video recordings that have been made are of particular importance. On 17-19/5/2004, musicologist Nikos Dionysopoulos recorded songs by Mustafá Ahmečik from Sminthi and Ferát Alí Aféndi from Áskira. Between 2002-2006, Dimitris Kitsikoudis filmed Pomak songs in the Pomak villages of Xanthi and in the Bulgarian part of Rhodope, during the production of the award-winning ethnographic documentary *Mlógo dúmiš mlógo*

pláčeš (The more you speak the more you cry)⁴. On 4/10/2016 Nikos Kipourgos filmed the Pomak musicians Ferát Alí Aféndi, Hasán Bojár, Mustafá Ahmecik and Eminé Buruǵí for the ERT 2 documentary "The secrets of music". The ethnographic documentaries and television productions made in recent years about the Pomak villages⁵ are of particular importance for the exploration of the modern way of life, but also for the traditional culture of the Pomaks.

Among the language editions, the books by Ritván Karahóǵa from Prosilio village stand out⁶ as well as the book written in 2006 by Sebaedín Karahóǵa. Ritván Karahóǵa also created the website pomlex.com in which he had posted part of his Pomak-Hellenic Dictionary, as well as his personal recordings of Pomak tales and songs. In Greek 2021, Ritván Karahóǵa published the improved and augmented electronic Pomak-Greek, Greek-Pomak dictionary *RodopSky Dictionary*, which contained 60,000 entries⁷.

In later years, the work of Panagiotis Papadimitriou⁸ gave a scientific dimension to the research of history, language and Pomak folk songs. Also, N.T. Kokkas edited many music publications and printed editions of Pomak fairy tales and songs, and published the three-volume work "Účem so Pomácko – Pomak Language lessons" (2004) as well as a number of folklore works on the oral tradition of the Pomaks⁹. In 2022 N. Kokkas published his book *The folk songs of the Pomaks of Thrace in the context of Balkan musical tradition*, in which he compared the songs of the Pomaks of Xanthi with the songs of the Balkans.

Unlike the Greek part of Rhodope, in Bulgaria numerous and systematic recordings of the ICH of the Pomaks have been made since the 19th century. Bulgarian musicologists and folklorists emphasized musical transcriptions, as well as the classification of themes, rhythms and metrical patterns, while creating valuable indexes that facilitate scientific research.

In Bulgarian literature there are extensive recordings and musicological analyses of the songs of the Pomaks, which Bulgarian musicologists and folklorists call "songs of Rhodope" (*Родопски песни*).

3. New technologies applied to the study and preservation of the cultural heritage of the Pomaks

3.1. "Thraki" Research Project

⁴ The documentary is available online at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wOMEmGsywFU&feature=emb_logo Accessed on 1/5/2023.

⁵ Among the ethnographic documentaries on the Pomaks, we mention the productions of Elena Horti ("Pomaks. The Indians of Thrace"), of Panos Papadopoulos & Fotini Tsibiridou ("Pomak wedding" - 2002) and of Stelios Lazaridis (A brave woman - *Enná jáka žaná*» – 2020). Among the television productions we mention the following: by Maya Tsokli ("Pomak villages of Xanthi" - 2001), by Dimitris Vrachiologlou (DELTA TV – 2008), by Nikos Aslanidis ("Real scenaria" ERT3 – 2010), by Stavros Theodorakis ("Protagonists" MEGA– 2013), by A. Guilot & M. Papadopoulos (*Grèce - La charia au coer de l' Europe* – 2014), by Center TV ("Without baggage in the Pomak villages" – 2016), By Thodoros Kalesis ("Balkan Express: The mountains of Bulgarian Rhodope" ERT 3 – 2018) and by Sophia Papaioannou ("360°: The Muslim minority in Thrace" - 2018).

⁶ *Pomak – Greek Dictionary* (1996), *Greek – Pomak Dictionary* (1998), *Basic Morphological Dictionary of Pomak* (2017). He also participated in the collective works *Grammar of the Pomak Language* (1996), *Pomak Language Syntax* (1997), *Greek – Pomak Dictionary* (1998).

⁷ see Karahóǵa Ritván (2021, 5 February). *Το λεξικό είναι εδώ!* (The dictionary is here) <https://pomlex.blogspot.com/2021/02/blog-post.html> Accessed on: 14/2/2021. See the online version of the dictionary at: Karahóǵa Ritván (2021). <https://www.rodopsky.gr/index.php> Accessed on 5/3/2021.

⁸ The following works are among the historical books written by Papadimitriou: Papadimitriou 2003- Papadimitriou 2008- Papadimitriou 2004: 209-235. Papadimitriou's works on the language of the Pomaks are: Papadimitriou 2008b- Papadimitriou 2013- Papadimitriou 2020: 149-166.

⁹ Kokkas 2004: 259-276- Kokkas 2006: 117-129- Kokkas 2007: 75-114.

In 1995 the "Thrace" project was launched, recording¹⁰ traditional songs from the Pomak villages Glafki, Oreon and Mikro Derio. A total of 38 research missions were carried out in 65 towns and villages of Thrace and the Thracian diaspora, including Thracian communities in Macedonia, as well as in Chernopolie, Ukraine. More than 2500 songs, instrumental scores and speech samples were recorded on 116 digital tapes of 130 hours and 1000 analogue audio cassettes of interviews. Visual material was also collected in approximately 400 hours of video footage and 12,000 photographs and slides. This material was indexed and sorted, after processing, into individual files.

In particular, special files are composed of: a) the full texts of the recorded songs, b) the translated texts of the foreign-language songs and their phonetic transcription in Greek alphabet, c) music recordings-parts in electronic transcription - in Finale program), d) the motion graphics, e) the final texts of the interviews, f) the recorded visual material (photo library - video library), g) the relevant bibliography, h) the data of Thracian associations in Greece and abroad.

Figure 2. Geographical navigation for "Xanthi" in the menu of the "Thraki" project. (<http://epth.sfm.gr/results.aspx> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

¹⁰ Liavas & Droulia 1999: 110- The full name of the project was: "Recording, studying and promoting the traditional music of Thrace". The recordings of the project, which was carried out in the period 1995-2000, are available online at: <http://epth.sfm.gr> Accessed on 1/5/2023.

ΕΡΕΥΝΗΤΙΚΟ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑ ΘΡΑΚΗ			
Research Data Form			
General Information			
Definition	Song		
Name / Title	Málka móma Dobruǵáncko		
Translation of name / Title	Málka móma 'míc, Dobruǵán'/'Dc		
Performance	Voice Only - Not Danceable		
Recording identification data			
Place	Kardhi, Prefecture of Xanthi		
Space	Στήη Κορθαίος, Κορθίν		
Date	12/11/1998		
Recording situation	Κατά μαζικόλο ηγούλοηον ΕΤΒ		
Singers	Μηουοί' Φοκί, Χάουο Χουοί'ν		
Data concerning song			
Language	Pomak		
Performance	Chorus, Not Antifuniko, One voice		
Data concerning Music			
Analysis of melody	Diatonic, D mode		
Music Genre	Table song		
Meter	Free		
Tempo	Rhythm	Value	Beats/min
	Not Free	Crotchet	90
Graphical analysis	A: : Málka móma Dobruǵáncko : B: : dar da ó vídan balóto kóte :		
Classifications			
By content	Love		
By performance	Table song, free rhythm		
Multimedia			
Sound (3:13)			
Score			
Lyrics			
Researchers	Haris Sarris, Lambros Liavas, Miranda Terzopoulou		
Data recorder	Yvuli Bayetalkou, Rose Sotirpoulou		
Date of entry	29/10/2002		

Figure 3. Research data form for the song “Málka móma Dobruǵáncko” in the “Thraki” project. (<http://epth.sfm.gr/card.aspx?mid=1510> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

The research team of the project was composed of anthropologists, ethnomusicologists, special collaborators, as well as young researchers and students, giving this research a comparative and interdisciplinary character. The team was divided into four sub-groups (Liavas, Droulia 1999: 13-17):

1. The singing group set the aim of studying the content of songs in their continuous transformations over time, with reference to their historical context, their performers and the conditions of their performance.
2. The music team sought to identify the most recognized folk instrumentalists in each region, both professional and semi-professional. Particular emphasis was placed on the techniques of playing and making musical instruments, while seeking out the instrument makers' areas of activity.
3. The dance group engaged in the synchronic study of dances. By looking for differences and specificities in movement, patterns, shapes and style, it shifted the focus of dance research from the level of the product to that of the process.
4. The fourth group emphasized the interpretive aspect of the musical elements of the research and in particular the narrative expression of musical experience and communication. It used research interviews and life narratives as its main methodological tool, approaching Thracian music as "cultural practices".

A large part of the material recorded by the “Thraki” project can be accessed through the Database which is integrated in the Great Music Library of the "Friends of Music" Association, located at the Athens Concert Hall.

3.2. “CT-Audio Link” project

In the years 2015-2016 the “CT-Audio Link” web project was carried out¹¹. The project included digitized recordings of Pomak songs and fairy tales, proverbs, wishes, curses and excerpts of spoken word.

¹¹ “Research Project: Improving the sound cultural links between different linguistic communities in Thrace”. The recordings of the project are available online at: <http://ct-audiolink.eee.uniwa.gr/index.php/> Accessed on 10/6/2023.

The project created a web site and a web application so that users would be able to access the cultural elements of various language communities through the recorded, transcribed and translated material of an appropriate database. The design and development of the site and of the application was done in such a way that the material is easily accessible and visible, so that users may easily identify the similarities and differences between the three language communities (Loukas et al 2016: 2). The International Phonetic Alphabet was used for the transcription of the texts.

The cultural elements recorded in the project include written texts, oral testimonies, images and audiovisual documents. Audio recordings include songs, fairy tales, proverbs, greetings, local cooking recipes and other traditional artifacts. CT-audiolink project focuses on highlighting relationships between communities. For this purpose, material belonging to the cultural traditions of the Greek-speaking community, the Turkish-speaking community and the Pomak community was collected and studied. From all the recorded audio material a selection was made based on certain criteria (Salakidis et al. 2016: 3):

- Acoustic quality of recordings.
- Recognisability of the local character of the material.
- Achieving a symmetrical representation of the different types of texts of the three communities so that the final material offered to and evaluated by users is as homogeneous as possible.
- Linguistic authenticity of the texts.

The menu of the <http://www.ct-audiolink.gr> website is located on the left side of the page and it is divided into five categories: ABOUT, CULTURAL MATERIAL, ACOUSTICS – SOUNDSCAPES, USEFUL LINKS, CONTACT. The ABOUT category consists of the subcategories: SCOPE, PARTICIPANTS, ANDROID MOBILE DEVICES APP, RESEARCH TEAM, FUNDING, PUBLICATIOIS, PUBLICITY, PROJECT PROGRESS. The category CULTURAL MATERIAL consists of the following subcategories: FAIRY TALES, SONGS, RECIPES, BLESSINGS / WISHES / CURSES / MALEDICTIONS, LULLABIES-DANDLING SONGS, PROVERBS, MISCELLANEOUS (Loukas et al 2016: 4-5).

Figure 4. Recipe for a traditional Pomak pie (klin) translated in Greek and Turkish (<http://ct-audiolink.eee.uniwa.gr/index.php/cultural-material/recipes/114-traditional-pie-klin-pomak> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

Figure 5. A Pomak folk tale (Pepe luhka – Cinderella) translated in Greek and Turkish (<http://ct-audiolink.eee.uniwa.gr/index.php/cultural-material/fairy-tales/158-2016-07-18-07-16-55> Accessed on 10/6/2023)

Figure 6. Pomak proverbs translated in Greek and Turkish (<http://ct-audiolink.eee.uniwa.gr/index.php/cultural-material/proverbs/143-proverbs-pomak> Accessed on 10/6/2023)

The overall aim of the “CT-AudioLink” project was to develop intercommunity communication links through technology. The research focused on the common acoustic aspects of the Greek, Pomak and Turkish traditions that coexist in Thrace in order to allow cross-cultural acoustic presentation, reference and access to important findings of the respective communities.

Two basic characteristics of the project are the open source approach used in the implementation of the technological tools and interfaces, and the open access to the material, mainly with the aim of using it as a cross-cultural reference in education.

4. The “Philotis” project

4.1. Main goals

“Philotis” is a 30-months research and development project implemented at the Athena-Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and

Knowledge Technologies / Xanthi's Branch. The aim of the "Philotis" project¹² is to create and distribute state-of-the-art spoken and textual annotated resources of living languages. "Philotis" project focuses on the creation of the infrastructure, the methodology and the tools for the recording, analysis and documentation of living spoken languages, with emphasis on idioms. The infrastructure is characterized by multimodal technologies (text, image, audio), while the tools will integrate into an advanced digital platform for language analysis and documentation using machine learning techniques. The goal is the successful integration of state-of-the-art technologies focused on recording of living spoken languages and their endowment with digital resources and tools.

The development support framework utilizes modern technology and adapts to the specific needs and characteristics of the individual languages, offering methodology, good practices and digital services. "Philotis" presents the dynamics to support excellence and business activity in the field of Language Technology, providing unique resources and cutting-edge technologies. At the same time, it employed specialized young scientists crossing the borders of the humanities and informatics. The technology used is scalable and reusable, which ensures its viability.

4.2. Project implementation

- Development of infrastructure for language, analysis and interpretation.
- Design and development of language resource
- Support for the development of resources
- Case study – Pomak
- Case study – Greek
- Copyrights clearance
- Integration and evaluation
- Development of analysis algorithms and language technology applications
- Development of tools for morphological analysis and lemmatization
- Multiword expression recognition with neural networks
- Development of chatbox system
- Development of web applications and hosting of language tools and of the language resource
- Dissemination
- Action plan for online dissemination
- Publications
- Subproject 2 Equipment
- Procurement of equipment

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¹² The official website of Philotis project is at <https://»Philotis«.athenarc.gr/the-corpus-of-pomak-language-is-online/> Accessed on 3/5/2023. see Krimpas et al. 2021· Karahóĝa et al. 2022· Karahóĝa, Markantonatou, Pavlidis 2022· Markantonatou et al. 2023· Stamou et al. 2022· Tsoukala et al. 2022. Tsoukala et al. 2023.

4.3. Morphologically annotated Pomak corpus

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The corpus of the corpus was based on various sources.

Legacy texts:

- in a variety of alphabets (Cyrillic, Greek, English-based Latin alphabet)
- sporadic transcriptions (and recordings) of Pomak folk songs and tales
- few modern journalistic texts and translations from Greek and English
- semi-automatically homogenised with the Karahóğa & Krimpas (K & K) orthography to form the raw Pomak corpus

Legacy texts were collected via a network of native speakers and Greek scholars. Copyright issues were resolved according to the Greek law to ensure free distribution for research purposes

Text types	Words	Places in Thrace
Folk tales	43,817	Emonio, Glafki, Dimario, Echinós, Myki, Pachni, Oreó
Language Description	19,524	mixed
Journalism	25,236	Myki
Translations into Pomak	24,208	Myki, Pachni
Folk songs	18,434	mixed
Proverbs	550	mixed
Other	5,325	Myki

Table 3: Pomak corpus: Type, size and geographical origins of texts.

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4.4. Gold annotated corpus on the UD treebank repository

The language resource is ready and openly available: it is a morphologically annotated corpus of Pomak with about 86,000 words. The new corpus has been uploaded on the Universal Dependencies treebank repository¹³, for international visibility and research availability. The progress of the project and the corpus can be followed at the treebank repository page.

During the project implementation there was collaboration of the ATHENA Research Centre with the community of Greek Pomak researchers and native speakers of the language. The outcome demonstrates the great potential of the application of artificial intelligence in the study and preservation of languages, as well as the dynamics of the researchers at the ATHENA Research Centre.

The treebank is licensed under the terms of Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike, CC BY-NC-SA 3.0.

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¹³ <https://universaldependencies.org/qpm/index.html> Accessed on 10/6/2023.

4.5. Multiword expressions documentation

The identification of the Pomak multi-word expressions (MWE) was based on four sources: a) interviews with native speakers, b) analysis of the Pomak Corpus, c) Ritván Karahóĝa's *RodopSky Dictionary*, d) the feedback during the collection procedure.

Targeted interviews with Pomak native speakers were carried out during the "Philotis" project. The native speakers were from four different Pomak villages of Xanthi (Selmá Karahóĝa from Púlevo / GR. Prosílio, Eminé Buruĝí from Demirĝík / GR. Dimáριο, Hasán Buyuklú from Bára / GR. Stírigma, Fehrí Imám from Bašájkoivo / GR. Mántena). The interviews explored the relevance of MWEs of Greek, Turkish, Bulgarian, Russian, English and other languages with the oral speech of the Pomaks of the Xanthi region. The interviews were recorded and analysed providing further information on the morphology, contextual use and semantic dimensions of MWEs with a great deal of illustrations.

The Philotis Pomak corpus offered a reliable database of linguistic material from a wide variety of sources. By searching the corpus with innovative computational tools it was made possible to locate MWEs within their context. Moreover, the studio recording of Corpus text excerpts and dialogues between native speakers facilitated the detection of further MWEs, which were thereafter added to an alphabetical list, translated and processed.

The digital Pomak-Greek RodopSky Dictionary by Ritván Karahóĝa (2021) was another important source of colloquial and idiomatic Pomak phrases. In the *RodopSky Dictionary* MWEs are provided at the end of each entry in orange colour, with a lot of cross references and examples. Karahóĝa's Pomak Dictionary makes it possible to inquire the origin of each entry, identify parts of speech and explore the interrelation of words among various languages.

In the procedure of registering synonyms and antonyms of MWEs even more expressions were added to the "Philotis" database and translated into English, Greek and Russian. Those expressions were initially set into alphabetical order. Then they were given to the native speakers for further analysis. After identifying the MWEs, their classification followed in a database containing the following fields:

- Serial Number, Interviewees, Date, Origin
- Pomak MWE , Greek translation, English translation, Russian translation
- Synonyms (in Pomak with literal translations in Greek, English and Russian)
- Antonyms (in Pomak with literal translations in Greek, English and Russian)
- Examples (in Pomak with literal translations in Greek, English and Russian)
- Equivalent phrase (in Greek, English and Russian)

S/N:	Interviewees:	Date:	Origin:	
Pomak phrase	POMAK	GREEK TRANSLATION	ENGLISH TRANSLATION	RUSSIAN TRANSLATION
Definition		LITERAL GREEK TRANSLATION	LITERAL ENGLISH TRANSLATION	LITERAL RUSSIAN TRANSLATION
Synonyms	POMAK	GREEK TRANSLATION	ENGLISH TRANSLATION	RUSSIAN TRANSLATION
Antonyms	POMAK	GREEK TRANSLATION	ENGLISH TRANSLATION	RUSSIAN TRANSLATION
Examples	POMAK	GREEK TRANSLATION	ENGLISH TRANSLATION	RUSSIAN TRANSLATION
Equivalent	POMAK PHRASE	EQUIVALENT GREEK PHRASE	EQUIVALENT ENGLISH PHRASE	EQUIVALENT RUSSIAN PHRASE

Table 4: Entry card for the classification of Pomak MWEs.

After filling in the respective fields in the database, the entries were transferred into the Pomak Idion database. The additional examples of synonyms and opposites of multi-word expressions provided by native speakers during the classification and lemmatization of Pomak MWEs enhanced the Pomak Idion reliability as far as the representativeness of entries is concerned.

IDION-Pomak: description

IDION is a lexicographic environment for the documentation of MWEs.

There are two interfaces of IDION-Pomak: one that is available to users who access the database only to look up a MWE (hereinafter: external users), and one that is used by the registered linguists who document the MWEs (hereinafter: encoders).

First, we present the interface available to the external users at <http://routing.athenarc.gr/>. For each documented MWE, Idion provides the following information:

1. Form, meaning, translation in a number of languages, one typical example of the usage of the expression on the Web
2. Technical information relevant to formal linguistic study and the usage of the content by Natural Language Processing (NLP) systems: which MWEs parts are fixed and which are not, if the order of the parts is fixed, morphological analysis, shallow syntactic analysis and alternative forms of the MWE, if they exist (inchoatives, passives, dative genitive form).
3. Semantic relations with other MWEs (synonyms, opposites, statives, possessives).
4. Sets of synonymous MWEs.
5. A set of syntactically and semantically correct usages of the MWE retrieved from corpora and the Web and a set of ungrammatical ones according to native speaker intuitions.

The interface supports searches by fuzzy matching retrieve MWEs in lemma form. In Fig. 7, the search is performed with the string “mi na” and four MWEs are obtained with their definitions. A translation of the MWE in Greek or English can also be accessed.

Expression	Definition	Translation
na dahóde mi na ustása	ne som hazýr da réčem nákvó	View translations
kápnaho mi nagýse	na daržót mo nagýse, na mózum da réčem nákvó illi da stórem nákvó	View translations
atóžnavá mi na dušóno	μου βαρβαίνει η ψυχή.	View translations
aléknava mi na dušóno	Húbovo mi stánava. Rahatladísavom.	View translations

Figure 7. Searches for external users supported by fuzzy matching at <http://routing.athenarc.gr/> (Accessed on 21/6/2023)

Once the desired MWE has been identified, other searches are available: variants (if any has been attested), gloss, translation, usage examples and their translations, morphosyntactic analysis of the variants and the usage examples in the Universal Dependencies framework (hereinafter: UD) and, synonyms and opposites, if any have been attested. Fig. 8 shows the tabs available once a MWE is selected. The selected MWE is indicated on the top left corner of the screen. In Fig. 8 the usage examples tab has been pressed and a set of examples is demonstrated along with their translations (also provenance information is available and analysis in the UD framework).

Variant: alóknava mi na dušóno

Definition: Húbovo mi stánava. Rahatládsavom.

Variants Examples Translations Lexical Variants Flexible usages Synonyms Other relations

Open in new tab

Examples

Example	Translations	Sc
Bajá tóglešo bóľko. Atkák stána ameleját alóknava mo dušæna.	View Translation	N
Čú mu glasáte i alóknava ji na dušóno.	View Translation	N
Vřitsi insános agá so naučót húbga habére alóknava mi na dušóno.	View Translation	N
Jálnys isái rábata da stáne vřistæm se alóknava dušóno.	View Translation	N
Súkür Allahá alóknava mi dušása. Stóre si vřít rábatýte.	View Translation	N

Figure 8. The examples tab has been pressed for the selected MWE *alóknava mi na dušóno*.

In Fig. 9 the searches for semantic relations among VMWEs are displayed for the VMWE *alóknava mi na dušóno*.

Variant: alóknava mi na dušóno

Definition: Húbovo mi stánava. Rahatladísavom.

Variants Examples Translations Lexical Variants Flexible usages

Open in new tab

Other Relations

Relation ↑↓	Expression
Opposite	izzéde mi dušóso
Opposite	izlíza mi dušása
Opposite	atóžnavá mi na dušóno

Remove tab

Synonyms

pačúnnavom ad uvótre
páda mi húbovo na dušóso
alóknava mi na dušóno
alóknava mi na dušása

Figure 9. Semantic relations between the MWE *alóknava mi na dušóno* and other MWEs.

The morphosyntactic analysis of MWE lemmata and their usage examples the UD framework (see Fig. 10) enables the processing of these constructs by state-of-the-art NLP tools.

Figure 10. UD analysis of the MWE “*zímom go ad ustána mu*”
(<http://routing.athenarc.gr/expression/pomak/2632> Accessed on 21/6/2023)

The interface which can be used by registered linguists (encoders) can be accessed at <https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr>. An auto-generated UD annotation is available here for each MWE. Fig. 11 shows the encoders interface where the UD analysis of a MWE is encoded in CONLLU format. [UD](#) is a framework for consistent annotation of grammar (morphology and syntax) across different human languages. UD is an open community effort with over 300 contributors producing nearly 200 treebanks in over 100 languages. [CONLLU](#) is the format of encoding UD annotation and it is readable by NLP machines.

Edit Lemma (#2735)

General Forms Use (obsolete) Glossing Relations UD Annotation Corpus Diagnostics HTML Comment Changelog

Conllu * 0 * Variant * Naválem ógne na glavóso

Comment autogenerated by python script

CoNLL-u *

```
# text = Naválem ógne na glavóso
# sent_id = 122
1 Naválem naválem VERB _ Aspect=Perf|Mood=Ind|Number=Sing|Person=1|Tense=Pres|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Act 0 root _
start_char=2571|end_char=2578
2 ógne ógan NOUN _ Case=Acc|Definite=Ind|Gender=Masc|Number=Sing 1 obj _ start_char=2579|end_char=2583
3 na na ADP _ _ 4 case _ start_char=2584|end_char=2586
4 glavóso glavá NOUN _ Case=Acc|Definite=Def|Deixis=Prox|DeixisRef=1|Gender=Fem|Number=Sing 1 obl:mod _
start_char=2587|end_char=2594
```

Figure 11. Auto-generated UD annotation for the MWE “naválem ógne na glavóso” in the Pomak Idion (<https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr/admin/?menuIndex=0&submenuIndex=-1&action=Edit&sortField=&sortDirection=DESC&page=1&referer=%252Fadmin%252F%252FmenuIndex%253D0%2526submenuIndex%253D-1%2526sortField%253D%2526sortDirection%253DDESC%2526page%253D1&entity=Lemma&id=2735> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

IDION Entities - Pomak

Cardinality

Additional conditions

Lemma id Unfiltered - exact match

Lemma Unfiltered

Usages Unfiltered - exact match

Relations Unfiltered - exact match

Distinct Rel. Unfiltered - exact match

Translations Unfiltered - exact match

Usages Unfiltered - exact match

Diagnostics Unfiltered - exact match

Diag. Examples Unfiltered - exact match

ID	Lemma	Usage examples	Relations	Distinct relations	Translations	Usages	Diagnostics	Diagnostic examples	Actions
2658	adglané mi so	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Edit
2567	adrom so rukava	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Edit
2694	adleté mi ad akylase	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	Edit
2713	aléknavá mi dušása	12	0	0	4	0	0	0	Edit
2719	aléknavá mi na dušono	17	5	2	2	0	0	0	Edit
2702	astájem nadzát paráklyte déne	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	Edit
2624	astájem bannóga da pacinne	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Edit
2631	astájem banóga da dúmi porf naprés	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Edit
2599	astájem nátko da varví havajá	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	Edit
2574	astájem nátko prez jezaladsavaje	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Edit
2561	atkáčem jazykate	1	1	1	7	0	0	0	Edit
2642	atpára mi glavána	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	Edit

The search for each lemma is carried out easily, as all lemmata are placed in alphabetical order (see Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Lemma search in the Pomak Idion (<https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr/admin/?entity=IdionMweCountView&action=list&menuIndex=11&submenuIndex=2> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

The examples provided for each entry help encoders clarify the use of every MWE (see Fig. 13).

The screenshot shows the 'Corpus' view in the IDION Entities - Pomak application. It features a search bar, filters for 'Additional conditions', and a table of corpus entries. The table columns include ID, Entry, Related lemma, Annotation, Retrieve Date, and Actions (Edit, Delete).

ID	Entry	Related lemma	Annotation	Retrieve Date	Actions
16752	Ty mo máksys prevádýs nah tam, ístís mizáivom da mi atvári belæ na glavóso.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16751	Namój so uruštisavá sas inazi, gába se si atvári belæ na glavóso.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16750	Atíde da stórem anó ekspirétsi za húbovo i atváresi belæ na glavóso.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16749	Atvárem belæ na glavóso agá se bórkam i ja sas komšójkana.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16748	Atvárem belæ na glavóso agá kupóvam brez hesáp.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16747	Atvárem belæ na glavóso agá ístam i ja da pómagnem.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16746	Kóikto belæ ni atfóho na glavóso i pak mi na stiga.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16745	Néma da so naučít níkuga dájma se mi atváret belæ na glavóso.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16744	Kakvó gáidí da atváres belæ insánome na glavóso.	atvárem belæ na glavóso		2022-10-23	Edit Delete
16742	Za sítkonosó nahóde kráj	nahódem krájene		2022-10-15	Edit Delete
16741	Móite so Alláh da u pamógne na nájdete krájete.	nahódem krájene		2022-10-15	Edit Delete
16740	Ja znóm, naj na sóname se mu nájdeme krájete.	nahódem krájene		2022-10-15	Edit Delete
16739	Katíri se nahóde krájene sas problémíte?	nahódem krájene		2022-10-15	Edit Delete
16738	Ne móžem da nahódem krájene vas vam.	nahódem krájene		2022-10-15	Edit Delete

Fig 13. Corpus examples for the MWE “atvárem belæe na glavóso”
 (<https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr/admin/?entity=CorpusView&action=list&menuIndex=3&submenuIndex=-1> Accessed on 10/6/2023)

The MWEs overview provides word statistics as well as top and bottom word frequency for the lemmata (see Fig. 14).

Figure 14. Lemmata word frequency in the Pomak Idion
 (<https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr/admin/aggregator/lemma/overview?menuIndex=11&submenuIndex=0> Accessed on 10/6/2023).

There is also an overview of the corpora showing the top word appearances for the corpora (see Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Corpora word frequency in the Pomak Idion
(<https://pomak.idion.athenarc.gr/admin/aggregator/corpus/overview?menuIndex=12&submenuIndex=0>
Accessed on 10/6/2023).

The relationship between Greek language MWE and Pomak MWE is clearly manifested in many cases. The linguistic relevance between the MWE of the two languages is due to the interaction between Greek and Pomak speakers across the ages. Here are some examples of MWE that have the same morphological and semantic patterns in both Greek and Pomak:

- *adbávem hatýrane* («destroy a favour», refuse somebody's wishes), Greek equivalent: *χαλάω χατίρι*.
- *astájem nadzát parátikyte déne* («leave bad days behind», forget the problems of the past), Greek equivalent: *αφήνω πίσω τα παλιά*.
- *čéftom balíkoso* («chisel wounds», go on hurting somebody, open old wounds), Greek equivalent: *ξύνω πληγές*.
- *glódom bannóga práve na ustáta* («look at somebody straight in the mouth», concentrate on what somebody is saying), Greek equivalent: *κοιτώ κάποιον στο στόμα, κρέμονται από τα χείλη του*.
- *hránem zmíje faf skútase* («feed a snake in my bosom», to befriend somebody who proves to be deceitful), Greek equivalent: *τρέφω φίδι στον κόρφο μου*.
- *iskárvom si hlæbase* («get my bread», earn my daily bread, make a living), Greek equivalent: *βγάζω το ψωμί μου*.
- *klávom bannóga na zahméte* («put somebody to strain», tire somebody, wear somebody down), Greek equivalent: *βάζω σε κόπο κάποιον*.
- *klávom dvéne nógy na annó amenýe* («put the two feet in one shoe», try to control somebody's life), Greek equivalent: *βάζω τα δυο πόδια σε ένα παπούτσι*.
- *plýem faf parý* («swim within money», be very rich), Greek equivalent: *κολυμπάω στα λεφτά*.

- *sabáre so dúnjása* (“the world is wasted”, there is extreme turmoil), Greek equivalent: *χαλάει ο κόσμος*.
- *sečé mi akýlos* (“my brain cuts, I am intelligent), Greek equivalent: *μου κόβει το μυαλό*.
- *síčkoso varví kríve* (“everything goes crooked”, everything goes wrong), Greek equivalent: *όλα πάνε στραβά*.

4.6. Speech technologies

+CHARA

process

Number of speakers

Recording hours

Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)

Speech-to-Text alignment

Text-to-Speech (TTS)

5. Interdisciplinary approaches to cultural heritage and popularization of scientific activity.

Intangible cultural heritage is more fragile and vulnerable because it is performed and lived by actors/members of communities, being shaped by social environments that are related to systems of knowledge, values, and cultural contexts. In most cases, its intergenerational transmission depends solely on oral and informal sharing. Therefore, the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage is different from the one done with other kinds of heritage as it relies on identifying, researching, collecting, documenting, archiving, transmitting, and protecting non-physical representations always aiming at the implementation of measures to ensure its viability through formal and non-formal education, as well as the revitalization of the various aspects of such heritage (UNESCO, 2003).

Intangible cultural heritage is transmitted to the next generations enriched by current experiences and practices thus providing communities with a sense of identity and continuity. Groups, and in some cases, individuals, recognize intangible cultural heritage as the most genuine representations of their identities as they illustrate their past and what makes them who and how they are in the present.

In consideration of the fact that cultural identity is inextricably linked to the safeguarding of ICH and to its transmission to future generations, modern society, with its typical models and customs, may lead to the cultural ‘extinction’ of peoples – considered as distinct social and cultural communities – which would be concomitant with the disappearance of their distinctive culture (Lenzerini 2011: 118).

The members of the “Philotis” research team cooperated in order to promote an interdisciplinary approach to the Intangible Cultural Heritage of the Pomaks. Computational Linguistics, Information Technology, Sociology and Ethnology were

among the disciplines that were applied during the implementation of the project in order to make the ICH of the Pomaks accessible to wide range of users.

5. Conclusion

Digital technologies can play an important role in the transmission of intangible cultural heritage. Research projects such as “Thraki” (1995-2000) and “CT-AudioLink” (2015-2016) carried out significant recordings of the ICH of the Pomaks. innovative projects such as “Philotis” provide access to cultural recourses that could not be easily accessed otherwise. Therefore, the use of new technologies for the preservation and dissemination of the intangible cultural heritage of the Pomaks has significant applications in the fields of sociological and linguistic research, folklore studies and education. The contribution of “Philotis” project (2020-2023) to the maintenance of the ICH of the Pomaks of Xanthi lies in the fact that through digital technologies, language, folklore and cultural knowledge can be better preserved and more effectively disseminated. The interdisciplinary approach of “Philotis” as well as the innovative tools that have been applied during its implementation render this project a significant attempt to promote the ICH of Thrace.

The protection of intangible cultural heritage requires the mobilization of citizens and governments and the development of official policies.

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